

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ALGORITHMIC KNOWLEDGE AND PROMPT FRAMING TO CRITICAL THINKING AMONG TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS IN CAGAYAN DE ORO CITY

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence has become a dominating force in people's lives, but the value of human knowledge must remain paramount. This study explored the relationship between algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing to critical thinking among teacher education students in Cagayan de Oro City. The study applied a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, using a researcher-made instrument. Random sampling was utilized to gather data from 110 fourth-year Bachelor of Elementary Education students. Results revealed high levels of algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, and critical thinking of teacher-education students. Furthermore, statistical analysis revealed a significant relationship between algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking, as well as between prompt framing and critical thinking. These findings suggest that preservice teachers with high levels of algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing tend to also demonstrate a high level of critical thinking. Finally, these results underscore the importance of integrating Data and AI literacy into teacher education programs and the strengthening of critical thinking facilitation, particularly in the dimension of evaluating arguments and assumptions.

Keywords: *algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, critical thinking*

INTRODUCTION

Technology continues to evolve and uphold its promise of making human life easier. Today, a new technology called artificial intelligence, or AI, has been introduced. This technology can copy how the human brain works, like how it learns, reasons, and decides (Balaquiao, 2024).

In education, artificial intelligence offers powerful ways to streamline processes and make them more efficient. It can design instruction that fits individual needs, provide real-time feedback, and adjust its delivery to fit learners' preferences. These truly led to attaining set outcomes and improving classroom engagement (Onesi-Ozigagun et al., 2024). Moreover, artificial intelligence has increased the automation of administrative operations, giving teachers more time and space to engage in meaningful interactions with learners (Balaquiao, 2024).

However, as with any advancement, it also carries unresolved issues yet to be recognized and addressed. These issues particularly point out algorithmic bias and data privacy (Chinta et al., 2023; Onesi-Ozigagun et al., 2024). Algorithmic bias is a type of bias produced by algorithms (Lendvai & Gosztonyi, 2025). This type of bias arises from inaccurate information used in training datasets. Moreover, this bias may increase prejudice, which in turn influences student assessment, content recommendations, and even access to opportunities (Seo et al., 2021).

These growing challenges require the development of algorithmic literacy. Algorithmic literacy is the ability to question, interpret, and interact with artificial intelligence (Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020; Zhang et al., 2023). Algorithmic literacy leads to algorithmic knowledge, a higher-level understanding of the systems behind digital platforms and tools. This type of knowledge enables learners to examine an algorithm critically (Hargittai et al., 2023; Ytre-Arne & Moe, 2023). Parallel to this is the emerging necessity for students to master AI prompt framing, a skill that significantly determines the accuracy and relevance of AI-generated content (Zaidi et al., 2023; ByteBridge, 2025). When learners learn to craft clear and purposeful prompts, they become better collaborators with AI, particularly in designing learning tasks or generating instructional materials (Tong, 2024).

To put it in context, in a study conducted by Sousa and Cardoso (2025), the majority of college students use AI tools in their academic routine for brainstorming ideas, writing assistance, content generation, and summarizing or simplifying complex materials. Wang & Li (2024) likewise reported that approximately two-thirds of college students use AI tools, with 63.11% of interactions involving assistance with completing assignments and 53.08% involving assistance with searching for necessary information.

At the very center of technological advancement, critical thinking remains a relevant skill. Filipino students, as studies unfortunately suggest, continue to demonstrate low proficiency in this area (Bernardo et al., 2023). However, structured pedagogies such as problem-based learning have shown promise in improving students' analytical and

evaluative abilities (Dela Cruz & Lapinid, 2022; Felix, 2023; Brazel, 2020). Importantly, critical thinking complements algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing, as students must evaluate AI outputs, identify flawed reasoning, and make ethically sound judgments in digital environments (Larson et al., 2024).

Despite ongoing studies on artificial intelligence integration, limited research exists on the relationship between algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, and critical thinking among students, particularly in Philippine education contexts. This research gap is significant, given the increasing reliance on AI tools across educational settings and the lack of structured interventions to develop learners' algorithmic competencies. Furthermore, most existing literature focuses on AI applications in higher-income countries, leaving a void in understanding its implications in resource-constrained or developing contexts.

The study aims to contribute to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education). The study supports SDG 4 Quality Education for the following reasons. First, the study helps enhance future educators' knowledge of algorithms and prompt framing. This will not only meet current needs but also enable them to be future-ready (Nyaaba, 2024). Second, the study will explore their current critical thinking skills, which are a core cognitive ability necessary for lifelong learning and informed decision-making (Sharma, 2024).

Thus, this study responds to these challenges and issues by examining more deeply the interplay among algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, and students' critical thinking. Moreover, this study seeks to address a knowledge gap by further determining the level of students' algorithmic knowledge, the extent of prompt framing, and critical thinking, and to contribute to the limited number of existing studies exploring these variables.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The study hypothesizes that algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing are significantly associated with the learners' critical thinking skills. This means that learners with higher levels of algorithmic knowledge are expected to demonstrate stronger critical thinking skills. The same goes for the extent of prompt framing, that if they have a high level of this, they also have a high level of critical thinking. The presented hypotheses are supported by three theoretical frameworks, which also serve as the study's main constructs.

The first theoretical framework is the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) by Punya Mishra and Matthew Koehler (2006). This framework outlines the triangulated areas of knowledge an educator must possess to integrate technology effectively into education (Backfisch et al., 2024). As future educators, their TPACK readiness reflects how algorithmic knowledge interacts with pedagogy and content mastery (Ali et al., 2023).

Its first area is Technological Knowledge (TK), which comprises one's knowledge of existing technologies, including hardware, software, applications, and information literacy. In addition, Hava and Babayigit (2024) introduced AI-technological Knowledge, which is under technological knowledge. Its second area is Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), which defines the purpose, values, and aims of education. This area also determines one's understanding of educational theories, teaching strategies, learning styles, classroom management, and assessment methods. The third area is Content Knowledge (CK), which describes one's mastery of content or the information crucial to one's field of expertise.

Algorithmic knowledge falls under technological knowledge (TK). TK in TPACK describes a preservice teacher's familiarity with digital tools, AI applications, and algorithms. Also, TK relates directly to algorithmic thinking, which involves awareness of AI logic (Yang et al., 2025); data literacy, which describes the capacity to interpret data-driven outputs (Holmes & Porayska-Pomsta, 2022); ethical awareness, which helps in ensuring responsible tech use (Zhu et al., 2025); human-AI interaction, which involves managing learner engagement with AI (Ning et al., 2024); and understanding AI applications, which describes practical knowledge of tools for teaching (Barman, 2024). Individuals who possess algorithmic knowledge are more adept at recognizing misinformation and digital manipulation (Zhang et al., 2023). When preservice teachers acquire algorithmic knowledge, they form a specialized TK that allows them to understand how AI systems process information.

Prompt framing falls under technological-pedagogical knowledge (TPK). TPK in TPACK describes a teacher's ability to formulate instructions or prompts with AI that produce appropriate teaching-learning activities and assessment tasks (Hamed et al., 2025). Desirable outputs are achieved only when prompts are clear, context-rich, and specific.

Critical thinking falls under technological-content knowledge (TCK) and pedagogical-content knowledge (PCK). Technological-Content Knowledge (TCK) helps teachers use technology to apply logic, infer, and interpret content meaningfully (MacCallum, 2025). On the other hand, PCK (Pedagogical-Content Knowledge) equips them to evaluate arguments and recognize assumptions within tech-mediated learning (Yue et al., 2024). When teachers use algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing effectively, they are engaged in higher-order thinking skills and reflective judgement (Lee & Palmer, 2025).

The second theoretical framework is Erving Goffman's Framing Theory (1974). This theory suggests that how information is presented to an audience influences the choices the audience makes about how to process it. It is an agenda-setting that not only tells the audience what to think but also how to think about that information. Frames are created by introducing information with predefined and narrow contextualization. There are several framing techniques, including the use of metaphors and stories.

Within Goffman's Framing Theory, algorithmic knowledge allows teachers to recognize the hidden frames created by algorithms; prompt framing describes how educators actively construct frames that guide AI outputs; and critical thinking enhances the ability to evaluate, challenge, and reframe these structures of meaning. Recent scholars converge on three key dimensions of prompt framing, such as clarity, context, and specificity (Cooper, 2023; Jacobsen & Weber, 2025; Viswanathan, 2025). Evidence shows that when a user identifies key parts of a prompt and includes them, the clarity and focus of results or outputs increase (Farrell et al., 2024). Furthermore, Zaidi et al. (2023) and ByteBridge (2025) presented evidence that AI users with stronger algorithmic knowledge are better able to construct effective prompts.

The third theoretical framework is the Revised Bloom's Taxonomy (RBT) of Anderson and Krathwohl (2001). This supports the assumption that prompt framing requires critical thinking, and the production of an effective prompt is a product of careful understanding of information, analyzing details that must be given relevance, evaluating the quality of construction, and creating an instruction that will best produce the desired results.

To describe in detail how this theory reflects the three variables, algorithmic knowledge primarily activates the lower- to middle-levels (remembering, understanding, applying, and analyzing), laying the foundation for higher-order skills. Meanwhile, prompt framing naturally fits across higher levels of RBT (applying and creating), since it requires careful design, evaluation, and synthesis of information. Lastly, critical thinking directly maps onto the top tiers of RBT (analyze, evaluate, create), representing the deepest forms of cognitive engagement.

Ghosh et al. (2024) further stated that a well-constructed question reflects good critical thinking skills. In addition, Helton (2024) cited that one's ability to evaluate and create lies in one's ability to understand and apply. This means that if one understands what it takes to formulate a good prompt and applies these characteristics when creating one, they can also evaluate its quality and create a well-constructed prompt. Cooper (2023) supports this in his framework by showing that prompt construction involves both lower and higher-order thinking skills. Writing prompts involve critical thinking as they require learners to define specific tasks, observe context, and formulate questions clearly.

The interplay among these variables has been documented in existing studies. Ytre-Arne and Moe (2023) found that students with higher levels of algorithmic knowledge demonstrated more reflective and strategic prompt construction when interacting with AI platforms, which, in turn, fostered stronger critical evaluation of AI-generated content. Hsu et al. (2023) also examined how algorithmic literacy, when paired with guided prompt activities, significantly enhanced university students' ability to analyze and critique AI outputs, denoting a compound effect between technical knowledge and framing skills in promoting critical reasoning. Likewise, Helton (2024) conducted a quasi-experimental study among senior high school students in Türkiye and concluded that structured prompt-framing tasks significantly improved learners' argument evaluation and logical reasoning, particularly when students were concurrently exposed to basic training in

algorithmic processes and data interpretation. These studies demonstrate that algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing do not operate in isolation; rather, they jointly activate and sustain the essential processes of critical thinking.

Together, these theories and empirical findings support the study's key assumptions: (1) that algorithmic knowledge enhances critical thinking; (2) that algorithmic knowledge informs prompt framing; and (3) that prompt framing helps initiate and strengthen critical thinking skills. Understanding the interplay among these constructs is vital to preparing learners for thoughtful, ethical, and informed engagement with artificial intelligence in educational settings. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual interaction among the study variables.

Research Questions

This study intended to determine the relationship between BEEd college students' algorithmic knowledge and the extent of prompt framing on their critical thinking. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the students' level of algorithmic knowledge?
2. To what extent do students demonstrate effective prompt framing?
3. What is the students' level of critical thinking skills?
4. Is there a significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking?
5. Is there a significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking?

Hypotheses

Research Questions 1, 2, and 3 are hypothesis-free.

Based on Research Questions 4 and 5, the null hypotheses were tested at the .05 level of significance:

Ho₁: The participants' algorithmic knowledge is not significantly associated with their critical thinking.

Ho₂: The participants' prompt framing is not significantly associated with their critical thinking.

Figure 1: Schematic Presentation of the Study

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the quantitative research design, specifically a descriptive-correlational research design, to determine the relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and the extent of prompt framing to their critical thinking skills. The descriptive-correlational research design allowed the researcher to observe the natural relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them, while measuring both the strength and direction of the relationship (Bhandari, 2023). This design was appropriate for the study's objective of examining how these variables were related in a real-world educational context.

Participants of the Study and Sampling Procedure

The participants in this study were fourth-year college students enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEd) program in Cagayan de Oro City who use digital devices (e.g., smartphone, laptop, tablet) and who access the algorithm-driven platforms regularly, such as search engines (e.g., Google), social media feeds (e.g., Facebook, TikTok), or AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Google Gemini).

The choice of BEd students was justified, as they are prospective educators who are likely to encounter AI-driven tools in their classrooms, making their understanding of algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking crucial to their teaching effectiveness (Lee & Palmer, 2025). Additionally, as future teachers, they would be directly affected by the integration of technology into educational practices, which is the focus of this study.

Moreover, this study used random sampling. The study participants were students currently enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education program in Cagayan de Oro City, as they are most likely to benefit from understanding the relationship between algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking in an educational context. On the other hand, the study excluded students who do not use AI chatbots at all, as their lack of exposure makes them less relevant to the research objectives. This approach helped gather data from individuals who were likely to apply algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, and critical thinking when using artificial intelligence and in their future teaching careers. Using Taro Yamane's formula with a population of 152 students and a 5% margin of error; hence, the calculated sample size was 110.

Research Instruments

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data. The development of the research instrument was guided by a synthesis of recent literature and established tools, particularly regarding the components and characteristics of the key variables. For the dependent variable, critical thinking, standardized instruments such as the Watson–Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal (WGCTA), the Cornell Critical Thinking Test (CCTT), and the California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) served as foundational references. For the independent variable, algorithmic knowledge, the items were formulated based on the “Digital Promise AI Literacy Framework” of OECD (2025) and the “AI Literacy Framework for Primary & Secondary Education” of Mills et al. (2024). Lastly, the design of items measuring prompt framing was influenced by applied and theoretical insights from various sources, including 1827 Marketing (n.d.), Polgov (2023), Cooper (2023), Brenkinfa (2024), and Farooqui (2024), all of which highlighted the characteristics of a good prompt.

After careful deliberation, the research instrument was streamlined into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire focused on algorithmic knowledge, covering five essential aspects: Algorithmic Thinking, Data Literacy, Ethical Awareness in AI, Human-AI Interaction, and Understanding AI Applications. Each aspect is measured using 4 multiple-choice items, for a total of 20 items in this part.

The second part focused on critical thinking, measuring five identified common subskills—Deductive reasoning, Evaluation of arguments, Inference, Interpretation, and Recognition of assumptions—which were aligned with the Revised Bloom’s Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). There were 10 multiple-choice items for every subskill, and a total of 50 items measuring critical thinking. Moreover, these subskills corresponded to the cognitive processes of understanding, applying, analyzing, and evaluating, thus ensuring consistency between the identified common subskills and the theoretical framework guiding the study.

The third part of the research instrument focused on the extent of prompt framing, which consisted of 15 items and collectively identified clarity, specificity, and context as the mutual and essential characteristics of effective prompts (1827 Marketing, n.d.; Polgov, 2023; Cooper, 2023; Brenkinfa, 2024; Farooqui, 2024). Each item was aligned

with one of these dimensions and was measured using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Slightly Agree (3), Agree (4), and Strongly Agree (5).

To minimize response bias, the questionnaire used neutral language and provided clear instructions to ensure that participants understood the questions without feeling pressured to provide socially desirable answers. The survey was kept concise to reduce fatigue, and participants were offered breaks during longer sessions. Clear withdrawal procedures were outlined, and support was made available when needed.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The validity of the research instruments was ensured through content validation with panel members and experts. Moreover, reliability was ensured by conducting the survey with a pilot group of 30 students, adhering to Bujang et al. (2024), which suggests a minimum of 30 respondents. In addition, Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient was used to assess reliability, with a value of 0.70 or higher deemed acceptable, as per Sheposh (2024). Finally, construct validity was ensured by running an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) after administering the survey. It is important to note that while it was ideal to have at least 200 participants for factor analysis, only 110 were gathered due to population constraints.

The results revealed that for algorithmic knowledge, the items were reorganized into three factors: *Applied Data and AI Literacy* (9 items), *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation* (4 items), and *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI* (3 items). Four items were excluded from the analysis. For critical thinking, the items were grouped into four factors: *Rule-Based Conclusions* (12 items), *Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions* (13 items), *Meaning & Generalization Critique* (7 items), and *Contextual Interpretation & Judgments* (9 items). Nine items were removed. As for prompt framing, the three original dimensions—*Context*, *Clarity*, and *Specificity*—remained, with only two items shifting from specificity to context.

Scoring Procedure

The results of the study were interpreted according to range and followed the corresponding qualitative descriptions and interpretations.

For the algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking, the study used the actual scores to analyze the results:

Score Range Interpretation

0.81–1	Very High
0.61–0.80	High
0.41–0.60	Moderate
0.21–0.40	Low
0.20 and below	Very Low

For the extent of prompt framing, the study used this system of scoring:

Range	Description	Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree	High
2.51 – 3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Statistical Treatment of the Data

For research questions one, two, and three, the study used descriptive statistics, specifically calculating the mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, to summarize and describe the level of algorithmic knowledge among students and students' critical thinking levels.

For research questions number four and five, the study used Canonical Correlation Analysis after ensuring that the data approximated the normal distribution. The Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) was used to examine the relationships between multiple independent and dependent variables simultaneously. This method allowed for a more holistic understanding of how algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing interact to influence critical thinking skills among students, offering deeper insights than simple bivariate correlation (McBride, 2025).

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the students' level of algorithmic knowledge?

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Students' Level of Algorithmic Knowledge in Each Component

Component s	Frequency & Percentage of Responses					M	Interpretatio n	SD
	Very High	High	Moderat e	Low	Very Low			
Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation	38 (34.55)	45 (40.91)	15 (13.64)	7 (6.36)	5 (4.55)	0.7 4	High	0.2 7
Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI	45 (40.91)	48 (43.64)	0 (0.0)	12 (10.91)	5 (4.55)	0.7 4	High	0.2 7
Applied Data and AI Literacy	33 (30.00)	37 (33.64)	30 (27.27)	9 (8.18)	1 (0.91)	0.7 0	High	0.2 1

Legend: .81-1=Very High (VH); .61-.80= High (H); .41-.60=Moderate(M); .21-.40= Low (L); 0-.20=Very Low (VL)

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Students' Level of Algorithmic Knowledge

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
13-16	Very High	43	39.09
10-12	High	45	40.91
7-9	Moderate	16	14.55
4-6	Low	5	4.55
3 and below	Very Low	1	0.91
Total		110	100
Overall Mean		11.46	
Interpretation		High	
SD		2.6	

Research Question 2. To what extent do students demonstrate effective prompt framing in terms of:

- 2.1 Clarity;**
- 2.2 Context; and**
- 2.3 Specificity?**

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Extent of Prompt Framing (Clarity)

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	41	37.27
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	41	37.27
2.51-3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate	17	15.45
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	4	3.64
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	7	6.36
Total			110	100
Overall Mean Interpretation				3.98 High
SD				1.04

Specific Indicators of the Demonstration of Effective Prompt Framing (Clarity)		M	Description	SD
1	I frame prompts using clear and familiar language.	4.08	Agree	1.18
2	I frame prompts that have easy-to-follow instructions.	4.04	Agree	1.20
3	I avoid vague or ambiguous terms when writing prompts.	3.96	Agree	1.05
4	I frame prompts that are easy to understand.	3.92	Agree	1.20
5	I ensure my prompts are free from grammatical or structural errors.	3.92	Agree	1.10

Table 4

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Extent of Prompt Framing (Context)

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	51	46.36
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	43	39.09
2.51-3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate	7	6.36
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	4	3.64
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	5	4.55
Total			110	100
Overall Mean Interpretation				4.17 High
SD				0.98

Specific Indicators of the Demonstration of	M	Description	SD
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Effective Prompt Framing (Context)					
1	I frame prompts that provide necessary information.	4.25	Agree	1.10	
2	I relate the prompt to real-life situations or current events.	4.25	Agree	1.16	
3	I frame prompts that contain examples.	4.17	Agree	1.09	
4	I align the prompt with the task's overall goals or outcomes.	4.16	Agree	1.12	
5	I frame prompts that state objectives.	4.14	Agree	1.09	
6	I frame prompts that contain relevant background.	4.10	Agree	1.07	
7	I consider the previous conversation with AI when framing prompts.	4.08	Agree	1.00	

Table 5

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Extent of Prompt Framing (Specificity)

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	47	42.73
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	43	39.09
2.51-3.50	Slightly Agree	Moderate	12	10.91
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	5	4.55
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	3	2.73
Total			110	100
Overall Mean Interpretation				4.15
SD				High
				0.96

Specific Indicators of the Demonstration of Effective Prompt Framing (Specificity)		<i>M</i>	Description	<i>SD</i>
1	I use precise wording to avoid multiple interpretations.	4.15	Agree	1.01
2	I break down complex prompts into simpler subparts when needed.	4.15	Agree	1.03
3	I include key details that guide the respondent's response.	4.14	Agree	1.07

Table 6

Summary Table of the Extent of Prompt Framing

Dimensions of Effective Prompt Framing	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Context	4.17	High	0.98
Specificity	4.15	High	0.96
Clarity	3.98	High	1.04
Overall Effective Prompt Framing	4.10	High	0.93

Research Question 3. What is the students' level of critical thinking skills?

Table 7

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Students' Level of Critical Thinking Skills in Each Component

Component	Frequency & Percentage of Responses					M	Interpretation	SD
	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low			
Rule-Based Conclusions	83 (75.45%)	20 (18.18%)	1 (0.91%)	5 (4.55%)	1 (0.91%)	0.87	Very High	0.18
Contextual Interpretation & Judgments	53 (48.18%)	42 (38.18%)	12 (10.91%)	2 (1.82%)	1 (0.91%)	0.79	High	0.18
Meaning & Generalization Critique	32 (29.09%)	31 (28.18%)	29 (26.36%)	9 (8.18%)	9 (8.18%)	0.62	High	0.24
Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions	16 (14.55%)	33 (30%)	21 (19.09%)	30 (27.27%)	10 (9.09%)	0.53	Moderate	0.25

Legend: .81-1=Very High (VH); .61-.80= High (H); .41-.60=Moderate(M); .21-.40= Low (L); 0-.20=Very Low (VL)

Table 8

Range, Interpretation, Frequency, and Percentage Distribution of the Students' Level of Critical Thinking Skills

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
33-41	Very High	37	33.64
25-32	High	52	47.27
17-24	Moderate	19	17.27
9-16	Low	2	1.82
8 and below	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		110	100
Overall Mean		29.2	
Interpretation		High	
SD		5.9	

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking?

Ho₁. There is no significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking.

Table 9

Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Students' Algorithmic Knowledge and Critical Thinking

Variable	Cross loading	R	R ²	F(12, 272)	p
Algorithmic Knowledge					
– Applied Data and AI Literacy	-0.575				
– Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation	-0.221				
– Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI	-0.190				
Critical Thinking		0.595	0.354	4.90**	.000
– Rule-Based Conclusions	-0.479				
– Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions	-0.395				
– Meaning & Generalization Critique	-0.388				
– Contextual Interpretation & Judgments	-0.348				

**significant at 0.01 two-tailed alpha level*

Research Question 5. Is there a significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking?

Ho₂. There is no significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking.

Table 10

Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Students' Prompt Framing and Critical Thinking

Variable	Cross loading	R	R ²	F(12, 272)	p
Prompt Framing					
– Clarity	-0.406				
– Context	-0.368				
– Specificity	-0.213				
Critical Thinking		0.494	0.206	2.44**	.005
– Rule-Based Conclusions	-0.136				

– <i>Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions</i>	-0.176
– <i>Meaning & Generalization Critique</i>	-0.008
– <i>Contextual Interpretation & Judgments</i>	-0.428

**significant at 0.01 two-tailed alpha level*

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the students' level of algorithmic knowledge?

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distributions of students' levels of algorithmic knowledge for each component. The three components, namely *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation*, *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI*, and *Applied Data and AI Literacy*, yielded means of 0.74, 0.74, and 0.70, respectively.

The results indicate two things. The first one is that the students have high levels of these three components. The second is that they possess these components of algorithmic knowledge in almost equal amounts. The standard deviations of *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation*, and *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI* of 0.27 suggest that the datasets are fairly consistent in the extent to which individual data points deviate from the mean. On the other hand, the standard deviation of 0.21 for *Applied Data and AI Literacy* is slightly lower, suggesting the dataset has even less variability.

Moreover, *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation* and *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI* got the highest means among the three identified components. *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation* explains how students' cognitive capacity to understand how algorithms work, paired with their vital role in ensuring accuracy, plays an important role in the use of algorithm-driven technologies. Guan et al. (2025) stated that students with higher levels of algorithmic thinking, or the capacity to recognize, design, and interpret algorithmic processes, tend to perform better in tasks that require oversight of automated systems and can more effectively detect errors or unintended outcomes. The results indicate that the students are knowledgeable about how algorithms work and recognize the role of human judgment in processing information or in interpreting outputs produced by artificial intelligence. On the other hand, *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI* measures how well students understand the role of artificial intelligence across diverse societal contexts, such as healthcare, education, and media. The result suggests they are aware of the different implications of AI systems across societal contexts. In the study by Usher & Barak (2024), they reported that the online explicit-reflective learning module significantly enhanced students' knowledge of AI ethics, and open-ended responses revealed students' increasing ability to identify and articulate concerns related to privacy breaches, the use of flawed datasets, and issues of biased social representation.

Furthermore, although *Applied Data and AI Literacy* did not have the highest mean, it is still high and just as close to the two highest components. *Applied Data and AI Literacy* assesses how much students know about data biases and the importance of human oversight. The result indicates that students have a high level of awareness of biases in data and of the importance of human oversight in data processing. Meletiou-Mavrotheris et al. (2025) mentioned in their study that across several of the framework's dimensions, particularly in questioning, data handling, and model interpretation, student teachers demonstrated increasing technical fluency and thoughtful reflection. Their projects reflected an appreciation for the importance of diverse and balanced datasets, and several groups analyzed model misclassifications with thoughtful attention to the impact of context, lighting, and visual similarity.

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students' levels of algorithmic knowledge. Results reveal that 39.09% of the students demonstrated a very high level of algorithmic knowledge, 40.91% a high level, 14.55% a moderate level, 4.55% a low level, and 0.91% a very low level. These findings indicate that students' understanding of algorithms vary widely, ranging from limited to advanced levels of awareness.

Similar variability was observed in the study by Lodhi (2025), where over 60% of students agreed or strongly agreed that they understood how algorithms determine the content they encounter online, although fewer than 20% strongly agreed, suggesting uneven depth of knowledge. In a broader cross-national study, Chung and Wihbey (2024) also reported significant differences in algorithmic knowledge among participants from the United States, the United Kingdom, Mexico, and South Korea, highlighting that perceptions of "high" and "low" algorithmic knowledge remain relative and context-dependent.

In addition, the overall mean of 11.46 conveys a high level of algorithmic knowledge. While it may be assumed that, in general, students possess this high level of algorithmic knowledge, the high standard deviation of 2.6 indicates that some students scored very high, others very low, and that the results are quite dispersed. Parke's (2025) study on algorithmic awareness and knowledge supports this interpretation. According to him, while the average score among university students in Hawai'i was moderate to high, there remains individual variability in how much students grasp algorithmic concepts.

Research Question 2. To what extent do students demonstrate effective prompt framing in terms of:

- 2.1 Clarity;**
- 2.2 Context; and**
- 2.3 Specificity?**

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the extent of prompt framing by clarity. The results show that 37.27% of the students demonstrated a very high extent of prompt clarity, another 37.27% showed a high extent, 15.45% indicated a moderate extent, 3.64% reported a low extent, and 6.36% reported rarely observing

clarity when framing prompts. An overall standard deviation of 1.04 suggests moderate variability in the students' responses, indicating they are clustered around the mean. Clarity is a fundamental instructional skill that teachers develop during preservice training, particularly when constructing directions and lesson objectives that are easy for learners to follow. This competence is similarly reflected in students' ability to formulate precise and understandable prompts.

Students with higher levels of prompt clarity also acknowledged that algorithms generate more accurate and appropriate results when prompts are well-structured and explicit. These findings are consistent with prior studies demonstrating that clear and structured prompts enhance algorithmic and AI-assisted task performance (Nugumanova, 2025; Dou & Rim, 2025). This finding indicates that the ability to formulate clear instructions, cultivated in teacher education through lesson planning and instructional design, may contribute to both students' self-reported prompt clarity and their perception of AI accuracy when using well-defined prompts.

However, a small portion of students did not demonstrate this skill consistently. Two possible explanations emerge: (a) limited awareness that well-articulated prompts yield better AI responses, and (b) difficulty in expressing intentions clearly through written instructions. Although the overall mean score of 3.98 indicates a high level of prompt clarity, the presence of students with lower awareness aligns with Xiao et al. (2025), who observed that even learners familiar with AI tools may struggle to craft effective prompts. Furthermore, Knoth (2024) reported that higher AI literacy is positively associated with improved prompt engineering performance, suggesting that students with less clarity may require more explicit instruction on how to communicate intent clearly when interacting with AI systems.

Moreover, students in general agreed with the five indicators of clarity in prompt framing, with an overall mean of 3.98, indicating a high extent of clarity in prompt framing. The first and the second statements got a mean of 4.08 and 4.04, which are the highest among the five statements. This implies that the students use clear and familiar words and construct their prompts with an easy-to-follow structure. It is also notable that the last three statements have a mean of 3.96, 3.92, and 3.92, respectively. These results can be drawn from the knowledge that, regardless of grammatical or structural errors and ambiguity, artificial intelligence and algorithms will find a way to understand the prompt. Interestingly, research shows that modern generative AI systems demonstrate robustness to grammatical or structural errors in prompts (Viveros-Muñoz et al., 2025). Nevertheless, ambiguity in intent and poorly structured prompts continue to pose challenges for AI interpretation (Keluskar et al., 2024).

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the extent of prompt framing across contexts. The results show that 46.36% of the students demonstrated a very high extent of providing context when framing prompts, while 39.09% exhibited a high extent.

These findings conveyed that most students intentionally include contextual information in their prompts, suggesting awareness that AI systems generate more accurate and relevant outputs when given sufficient background or situational details. This practice reflects students' understanding that specifying the task's purpose, setting, or intended audience enhances the quality and appropriateness of AI-generated responses.

Another plausible reason for this behavior is the students' effort to minimize AI follow-up queries. When a prompt lacks sufficient contextual detail, AI systems often request clarification to ensure accurate task completion. This observation aligns with studies showing that individuals with higher AI literacy tend to use descriptive, context-based prompts to achieve more precise, relevant outcomes (Kim et al., 2025). Similarly, Knoth (2024) emphasizes that aligning prompts with contextual goals is a key characteristic of effective prompt engineering.

Meanwhile, a smaller proportion of students exhibited moderate (6.36%), low (3.64%), and very low (4.55%) levels of contextual inclusion. One possible explanation is that some students use AI primarily to generate short, straightforward outputs that may not require detailed context. Peters et al. (2025) observed that task complexity influences prompt design—short factual or procedural requests often omit contextual details without significantly affecting accuracy. However, this practice has potential drawbacks: as Çelik (2024) notes, insufficiently contextualized prompts can lead to overly general or verbose AI responses, and in some cases, outputs that fail to match the user's reading level or intended audience.

Moreover, the overall mean of 4.17 indicates that students had a high extent of framing prompts in context, with an overall standard deviation of 0.98 indicating a moderate spread in the data. This result can be supported by the availability of learning resources focused on artificial intelligence and AI chatbots. With increasing media consumption, the integration of this topic into mainstream media could have led to a rich understanding of the utilization of AI chatbots like ChatGPT, Gemini, and Copilot. Research indicates that higher levels of AI literacy are associated with better prompt-engineering practices (Knoth, 2024) and that educational settings are increasingly emphasizing proficiency in prompt framing and AI tool use (Walter, 2024). Therefore, the high mean observed aligns with broader trends in AI education and media exposure.

Furthermore, the students generally agreed to all statements under this component. However, it is notable that the statement receiving the least agreement is the statement, "I consider the previous conversation with AI when framing prompts." This statement got the lowest mean of 4.08. It can be observed that when using AI chatbots, they automatically open a new conversation every time you open an AI chatbot application or visit an AI chatbot site. Another point to consider is that free accounts usually limit the conversation and would require the user to open another conversation, since it's a premium service to keep the conversation going for better output. This may lead users to avoid considering previous conversations and instead create a new one immediately. Research on conversational agents shows that a lack of continuity (i.e.,

starting fresh without history) can undermine user trust and increase the number of queries required to complete tasks (Guo et al., 2020; & Scherr, 2025). While the specific effect of free-account limits on conversation resetting is underexplored, the pattern of fresh-start chats aligns with broader findings on interaction discontinuity in AI systems.

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the extent of prompt framing by specificity. The majority of the students (42.73%) had a very high tendency to provide specific details when framing prompts, and the second-highest percentage (39.09%) had a high tendency to practice this component.

These results demonstrate that students are aware that providing specific details in framing prompts are crucial to getting appropriate outputs. This aligns with recent research defining prompt literacy as the ability to generate and iteratively refine precise prompts (Tour, 2025), and empirical evidence showing that structured prompt-engineering training enhances prompt quality through specificity, clarity, and relevance (Woo et al., 2024).

On the other hand, some students had a moderate to very low level of specificity when framing prompts. Results further show that 10.91% had a moderate extent of framing prompts, 4.55% had a low extent, and 2.73% a very low extent. The reason behind this could be AI chatbots' tendency to provide responses regardless of how detailed the prompt is (Sawalha, 2024). For instance, a single word could already serve as a prompt, and AI will explain as much as it can to the user. When the user is not convinced of the output, they can just prompt with more specific details (Woo et al., 2024).

Moreover, all three statements had almost the same mean of 4.15, 4.15, and 4.14, respectively. Students observe and practice precise wording, a simpler structure, and the inclusion of key details when framing prompts. This finding highlights a common understanding of how essential specificity is in prompt framing. This aligns with broader research indicating that prompt quality, especially clarity and specificity, is a critical component in obtaining accurate, relevant responses from AI systems (Federiak, 2024; Knoth, 2024; Covino, 2025).

In general, the students had an overall mean of 4.15, indicating a high level of specificity in prompt framing. In addition, a standard deviation of 0.96 suggests that the students' responses were clustered or nearly identical.

Table 6 presents the summary table of the extent of prompt framing. On a 5-point Likert scale where 1 means Very Low and 5 means Very High, *Context* had the highest mean of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.98, suggesting moderate variability. This finding illustrates that, in general, students provided a high level of context when framing prompts.

Next in the order is *Specificity*, with a mean of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 0.96 (moderate variability), which is almost the same as context. This indicates that, in addition to ensuring context is included in the prompt, students also demonstrated a high

level of specificity in their observations and practices. The least among the components is *Clarity*, with a mean of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 1.04, suggesting more variability in how respondents rated the clarity of their prompts. The reason is AI's powerful, adaptive tokenization process, which breaks text into smaller units (Cooper, 2023). While tokenization mitigates some clarity/syntax issues, clarity still matters because context, specificity, and clarity are all interrelated. AI will process the prompt word by word and will make sense of the general idea.

In general, the extent of the students' prompt framing was high, with an overall mean of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.93, suggesting a relatively low variability. These results suggest that students are generally knowledgeable about how to achieve better outputs from AI chatbots by paying attention to context, specificity, and clarity.

Research Question 3. What is the students' level of critical thinking skills?

Table 7 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the students' level of critical thinking skills in each component. There are four identified components under critical thinking, namely Rule-Based Conclusions ($\bar{x}=0.87$), *Contextual Interpretation & Judgments* ($\bar{x}=0.79$), *Meaning & Generalization Critique* ($\bar{x}=0.62$), and *Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions* ($\bar{x}=0.53$). Results show that the students achieved very high levels of Rule-Based Conclusions with minimal variability (SD = 0.18), and high levels of Contextual Interpretation & Judgments (SD = 0.18, very low variability) and Meaning & Generalization Critique (SD = 0.24, low variability). These show consistent variation in the results, as indicated by their respective standard deviations. Moreover, these results demonstrate that the students were highly capable of deductive reasoning, interpretation, and evaluation, which are key skills for a teacher-education program to deliver instruction and administer various types of assessments. On the other hand, the students scored at a moderate level on *Evaluating Arguments & Assumptions*, with a standard deviation of 0.25, suggesting low variability. According to Kusi et al. (2024), preservice teachers exhibited stronger deductive reasoning and interpretation skills than evaluative reasoning, as they often found it difficult to assess assumptions and judge argument validity without explicit language scaffolds. Although this doesn't necessarily indicate they perform poorly in this component, more intervention is needed to strengthen their skills in evaluating arguments and analyzing assumptions.

Another angle to consider is their linguistic capacity. Arguments are technical in nature, and assumptions are drawn from how words are stated. This component of critical thinking is dependent on syntax and semantics. From a linguistic perspective, it seems intuitive that a strong link would exist between linguistics study and CT; thus, the study reveals a variety of aspects of linguistics tasks and classroom activities where the link is significant, including several specific CT skills and dispositions that are related to linguistics teaching and learning (Vo & Moore, 2024).

Table 8 reflects the frequency and percentage distribution of the students' level of critical thinking skills. The results show that 33.64% of the students had very high levels of critical thinking; 47.27% obtained high levels; 17.27% got moderate levels; 1.82% had

low levels; none had very low levels. Based on this result, the majority of the students had excellent levels of critical thinking.

However, 1.82% fall into the low-level critical thinking category. Even though this is minimal, the implication is still alarming because the students are soon to be teachers. The same observation is reflected in the study by Çarkıt & Kurnaz (2022), which reported various mean scores for sub-dimensions of critical thinking among pre-service teachers, supporting the idea that most teacher-candidates possess relatively strong critical thinking dispositions.

Furthermore, an overall mean of 29.2 indicates that students' critical thinking was high. However, the variation of this is quite high, with a standard deviation of 5.9. This means that students' levels of critical thinking range from low to very high. This also leads to the realization that, even after three years in higher education, critical thinking may still not be fully developed. Enabling critical thinking development in higher education: Golden (2023) reports that, even within initial teacher education programs, critical thinking development remains uneven and calls for targeted interventions.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking?

Ho₁. There is no significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking.

Table 9 presents the results of the canonical correlation analysis between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking. The p-value of 0.000 is below the 0.01 significance threshold. This result denotes that the relationship between the students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) can be rejected; hence, there is a significant relationship between students' algorithmic knowledge and critical thinking. Several implications can be drawn from this. First, critical thinking may be enhanced by improving algorithmic knowledge. Second, critical thinking may be enhanced if educational programs prioritize the development of algorithmic knowledge. Lastly, critical thinking can be enhanced by teachers if they also assess algorithmic knowledge alongside.

Moreover, the canonical correlation coefficient of 0.595 indicates a moderate to strong linear relationship between the two sets of variables. In addition to this correlation, an R² value of 0.354 means that 35.4% of the shared variance in critical thinking, which is a moderate proportion, can be explained by algorithmic knowledge. The remaining 64.6% of the variance in critical thinking is due to other variables or factors not accounted for in the analysis, as critical thinking is a complex trait influenced by a wide range of factors beyond algorithmic knowledge (Cui & Zhao, 2024).

Moving on to the contributions of each variable, or cross-loadings, it is important to note that negative cross-loadings indicate that higher scores in one canonical variate correspond to lower scores in the other, depending on the scaling. But this doesn't imply

an inverse relationship. Rather, it indicates the direction of association within the canonical model. Among the algorithmic knowledge dimensions, *Applied Data and AI Literacy* has the strongest contribution at -0.575. *Algorithmic Reasoning and Human Mediation* at -0.221 and *Contextual and Ethical Understanding of AI* at -0.190 contribute less. On the other hand, among critical thinking dimensions, *Rule-Based Conclusions* at -.0479 and *Evaluating Arguments and Assumptions* at -0.395 are most associated with algorithmic knowledge.

In summary, students with higher algorithmic knowledge, especially in data literacy and AI understanding, tend to exhibit higher levels of critical thinking, particularly in rule-based conclusions, and in evaluating arguments and assumptions. Furthermore, this implies that algorithmic knowledge enhances analytical and evaluative skills, which reinforces the importance of integrating AI literacy and critical thinking into education. Milberg (2025) noted in his study that AI literacy in education is increasingly recognized as not just about tool use, but also about fostering critical thinking, evaluative reasoning, and data awareness. Learners who understand how AI works are better placed to exercise judgment about outputs and implications (Milberg, 2025). In addition, Morris (2022) mentioned that teaching algorithmic literacy within a media literacy program helps learners not only understand how algorithms shape content but also to question and interpret the mechanisms, thereby enhancing their critical thinking abilities.

Research Question 5. Is there a significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking?

Ho₂. *There is no significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking.*

Table 10 presents the canonical correlation analysis between students' prompt framing and critical thinking. The p-value of 0.005 is less than the 0.01 alpha level, which indicates that there is a statistically significant canonical relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) can be rejected, denoting that there is a significant relationship between students' prompt framing and critical thinking. Several implications can be drawn from this. First, how prompts are framed in educational settings may enhance students' critical thinking skills. Second, incorporating prompt framing in the curricula may foster critical thinking. Lastly, teaching students the skills of framing their own prompts may empower them to take more control in developing their critical thinking.

In addition, the canonical correlation coefficient of 0.494 indicates a moderate association between the two sets of variables. Also, the R² value of 0.206 means that 20.6% of the variance in critical thinking, which is a moderate proportion, can be explained by prompt framing. The remaining 79.4%, which is a large portion, is influenced by other factors.

Moving on to the contributions of each variable or cross-loadings, as in the prior analysis, negative values indicate the direction of association, not necessarily an inverse

relationship. Among the dimensions of prompt framing, Clarity at -0.406 contributes the most to the canonical function, followed by context at -0.368, and specificity at -0.213. These results suggest that how clearly, contextually, and specifically students frame prompts relates meaningfully to their critical thinking ability. On the other hand, among the dimensions of critical thinking, *Contextual Interpretation and Judgments* at -0.428 have the highest loadings, indicating that they are most strongly associated with prompt framing. This is followed by *Evaluating Arguments and Assumptions* at -0.176 and *Rule-Based Conclusions* at -0.136. These dimensions also show moderate associations. Finally, the *Meaning and Generalization Critique* at -0.008 contributes minimally.

In summary, students who frame prompts more clearly, contextually, and specifically tend to demonstrate higher levels of critical thinking, particularly in making contextual judgments, evaluating arguments and assumptions, and drawing logical conclusions. This conclusion conveys that effective prompt framing is linked to the students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and reason critically. Such a finding aligns with the study of Walter (2024), espousing that prompt engineering in education emphasizes that students don't just use AI tools; they must learn to craft prompts. In doing so, they perform higher-order cognitive work: designing the prompt involves abstraction, refining the prompt involves analysis, and evaluating the AI's output involves judgment and critique.

Conclusions

The objective of the study was attained, demonstrating that teacher education students possess strong competencies that are increasingly essential in an AI-integrated learning environment. The study concludes the following:

First, the students have a high level of algorithmic knowledge, which is a result of rich integration of algorithms in day-to-day experience. Even though algorithmic knowledge is not directly taught and included in the curriculum, their interaction with the internet and social media in general has helped them grasp the mechanisms of algorithms embedded in their experience.

Second, the students have a high extent of context, clarity, and specificity when framing prompts. These are criteria for ensuring quality and appropriate outputs when interacting with AI chatbots. This result can also be attributed to teacher education's intervention of regular practice and development in the field of language and communication, as this field is among the most relevant aspects of becoming an excellent educator.

Third, critical thinking among teacher-education students is considered high. This can be attributed to the program's practices that allowed the students to enhance their cognitive abilities. As preservice teachers, they undergo plenty of reading, preparation, and execution of skills that require a comprehensive amount of mental exercises.

Fourth, students with stronger algorithmic knowledge, especially in *Data Literacy and AI Understanding*, tend to exhibit higher levels of critical thinking, particularly in *Rule-*

Based Conclusions. Students who develop algorithmic knowledge are challenged to understand abstract concepts, which strengthens their logical ability and, in effect, improves their critical thinking.

Fifth, students who frame prompts more clearly, contextually, and specifically tend to demonstrate higher levels of critical thinking, particularly in *Making Contextual Interpretation and Judgments*. Clarity and precision of thoughts allow students to articulate their ideas, which is a key aspect of critical thinking.

Sixth, the theoretical frameworks referenced in the study explain the results. The Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework of Punya Mishra and Matthew Koehler (2006) reflected how algorithmic knowledge under Technological knowledge interacts with pedagogical mastery, manifested by instructional planning through effective prompt framing. This also shows how algorithmic knowledge and prompt framing correlate with critical thinking, as both processes require logical abilities. In addition, Erving Goffman's Framing Theory supports the idea that AI users who have better algorithmic knowledge are more capable of constructing effective prompts. Furthermore, Anderson and Krathwohl's Revised Bloom's Taxonomy (2001) supports the assumption that prompt framing requires critical thinking, and the production of an effective prompt is a product of careful understanding of information, analyzing details, and creating and evaluating the quality of prompts that best produce the desired results.

In a nutshell, algorithmic knowledge, prompt framing, and critical thinking have good starting points in the teacher education program, and they are all linked to each other. Even though they are not directly taught or explicitly embedded in the curriculum, the students have demonstrated high levels of these variables. Thus, attention, inclusion, and enhancement of these variables should be given relevance in order to make sure that the teacher education students are fully ready to meet the demands of both the present and the future.

Recommendations

The study's findings and conclusions led to the following suggestions, which are offered for consideration:

1. School administrators may consider formulating a policy that serves as a roadmap emphasizing the training and development of AI literacy, prompt design, and facilitation of critical thinking, and their integration into the curriculum to ensure shared ownership, highlighting ethical guidelines for AI use in teaching and learning.
2. Teachers may integrate AI literacy into their lessons and apply strategies that improve critical thinking, especially in the dimension of evaluating arguments and assumptions.

3. Students may practice framing prompts with context, clarity, and specificity to improve their articulation of ideas and produce appropriate outputs.
4. Future researchers may replicate the study on a wider scale.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained ethical clearance from the institution's Research Ethics Committee (REC) to ensure that the study met the established ethical standards and upheld the principles of responsible research. Following REC approval, the researcher secured the endorsement of the dean to confirm the study's scholarly merit and its alignment with the institutional mission and quality assurance protocols.

To facilitate smooth, non-disruptive data collection, the researcher coordinated with course instructors to schedule the research test during class hours. This coordination respected instructional time and ensured that participation was accessible without interrupting planned academic activities. Such procedures upheld the principle of justice by promoting fair access and equal opportunity to participate in the research (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979).

Furthermore, this study modeled the Belmont Report's Core Principles by following these ethical guidelines:

First, before distributing the questionnaires, a brief introduction and orientation were conducted to inform participants of the research's purpose, data collection procedure, and the intended use of the results. This was made to ensure respect for persons, promote well-being through beneficence, and uphold justice through lawful and honest research practices.

Second, all participant data was anonymized using identification numbers, and no personally identifiable information was stored or shared. Moreover, the questionnaire included a consent form and enumerated rights, indicating voluntary participation, withdrawal without penalty, and assurance of confidentiality.

Third, if a participant withdraws, their data will be excluded from the study's final analysis, per the ethical guidelines. Participants were informed about their right to withdraw at any time without any negative consequences, and this was clearly stated in the informed consent form.

Fourth, proper data management and disposal were observed. The data would be retained for 2 years after the completion of the study to allow for future verification of results, publication, and addressing of any post-study inquiries. After this period, the data would be securely destroyed (e.g., deleted from storage devices or shredded if physical). These are foundational guidelines for ethical conduct in human subject research (National Commission, 1979).

Lastly, the results were shared with the participants and stakeholders. The participants received a summary of the study's findings, which was also shared with relevant educational stakeholders and the local community. Results were disseminated through academic publications, presentations at educational conferences, and possibly via the institution's website. This ensured that the study's outcomes contributed to improving educational practices and policy in the region.

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